

MANDIBULAR THIRD AND SECOND MOLARS HORIZONTALLY IMPACTED: A CASE REPORT**Antoine Berberi,***BDS, MSc, PhD, HDR. Professor, Head Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Lebanese University
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7584071>***Abstract**

Impacted permanent mandibular second molars do not occur frequently. However, when they do, they can present a serious treatment problem, particularly when associated with an impacted third molar, especially in a horizontal position. Various explanations of the anomaly have been proposed. This paper aims to report a case and describe the reasons of disturbed eruption of the permanent lower second molar.

Keywords: Second molar, third molar, impacted, mandible, extraction.

Introduction:

The impaction of the mandibular third molar is very frequent and represents a particular pathology. However, impaction of the mandibular second molar is very rare [1], with an incidence of 2/1000 [2] and 1.36 / 1000 [3] and higher rates of unilateral than bilateral impaction. Its advent poses problems of variable severity, most often benign, but sometimes serious [4]. The therapeutic means are [5-8]:

- Abstention: rarely justified for general or local reasons; it is most often a postponement of the intervention;

- Repositioning on the arch, its indications are developing with the extension of dento-maxillofacial orthopedics but remain limited by the need for very specific conditions (position, place, motivation, hygiene, age and cost of the treatment).

- Reimplantation, the indications of which are very limited and the success is unpredictable.

- Surgical extraction.

Before presenting our clinical case, it seems interesting to review the etiopathogenesis of the inclusions of these mandibular molars.

Etiopathogenesis:

The inclusion of a tooth is above all linked to a disorder whose consequence is the rupture of the usual and normal phenomena of the eruption [3,9]. This may involve one or more of the following factors: the germ, the alveolar bone, the gingival mucosa and maxillo-mandibular facial growth.

• The germ may be "unfit" for the eruption. It may have a coronary or radicular anomaly, the cause of which is often an early trauma. It may also be abnormal. Moreover, the evolution of the germ can be disrupted by the presence and increase of tumoral or pseudo-tumoral phenomena [3,9,10].

• The alveolar bone: the vertical growth of the alveolar processes, associated with an abolition of the osteogenic function of the periodontium is a factor of inclusion. The rearrangements of the lateral walls of the alveolus are constant as long as the tooth has not encountered an impassable obstacle or is not functional [2,3,10].

• The gingival mucosa plays an important role at the terminal period of the eruption and can be considered as responsible for the fibro-mucosal inclusion [2,10].

• Maxillary and facial growth: dento-maxillary disharmonies represent an important cause of dental inclusions. In molar regions, posterior growth insufficiency or posterior crowding syndrome is a significant factor in second and third molar impaction [11].

This factor is therefore the consequence of a lack of space which may be temporary or permanent.

There are also general inclusion factors. Hereditary factors seem to play an important role.

Multiple inclusions seem to come from these causes where the genetic disorder affects both the dental lamina and the alveolar bone independently of any mechanical obstacle [11-13].

Case Report:

Mr. R., aged 29, was oriented to our clinic by his dentist, for inclusion of the mandibular wisdom teeth. The questionnaire evokes repeated infectious accidents linked to the eruption of his molars.

Facial examination shows mandibular retrognathia and maxillary prognathism.

The clinical examination reveals that the two mandibular wisdom teeth are wedged, the 48 in horizontal position, the 38 in vertical position, those of the maxilla (18,28) are on the arch and in good position. We also note the absence of the two second mandibular premolars (45 and 35) and of the right mandibular molar (47) associated with the presence of the deciduous molar on the right side (Fig. 1).

Note an accentuated dental overlap at the level of the maxilla.

The panoramic X-ray reveals (Fig. 2) that the second right mandibular molar (47) is included in a horizontal position apparently pushing back the lower dental canal towards the basilar rim and is superimposed on the third molar. The latter is also enclosed in a horizontal position. It also shows the agenesis of the two second mandibular premolars (45,35). The patient showed no signs of labio-mental paresthesia.

A CT scan is requested, with axial and coronal sections spaced 2 mm apart, real size, with panoramic reconstructions.

Axial sections revealed the presence of a cystic radiolucent image, suggestive of a peri coronal cyst, which encompassed the crown of the impacted right second molar and the apex of the distal root of the first molar (Fig. 3).

The para-axial sections of the scanner highlight, on the right side, an intimate relationship between the impacted second molar and the lower dental canal. One of the cuts shows a rupture of the roof of the lower dental canal. The third and second molar are separated by a thin layer of bone.

On the left side, the sections show that the apices of the third molar and the inferior dental canal are separated by a thick framework of bone (Fig. 4).

A sagittal reconstruction of the CT scan showed the ultimate position of the impacted molar with the mandibular canal (Fig. 5).

After an in-depth analysis of the radiographic assessment, we decided to extract the mandibular second and third right molars and the third left molar.

Surgical Procedure

Faced with the patient's anxiety and the deep position of the impacted second molar, we decided to operate under general anesthesia.

The incision was of angular type, performed with a n°15 blade. The horizontal segment of this incision extends from the retromolar region to the mesial aspect of the first molar on the right side. The discharge line frankly extends the incision to the bottom of the vestibule.

After lifting the flap, it is loaded in a complete, safe and atraumatic way, on a retractor.

With a round surgical bur, on a handpiece with abundant irrigation in sterile saline solution, we released the third molar which is easily extracted with a

rocking movement from bottom to top and from front to back with an elevator.

At this moment we discovered the bone frame that separates the two molars. With the same bur, the impacted second molar is fractioned (Fig. 6 and 7). Once cleared, with a fissure bur, we partially separate the crown from the root. This separation is completed by fracturing the tooth using an angled elevator. Then, the crown and the roots are extracted separately.

A part of the inferior dental nerve is visible for a few millimeters in length (Fig. 8). A very meticulous curettage of the region as well as the apex of the distal root of the first molar is performed. The regularization of the bone with a bone rasp is completed as well as washing with saline solution. Finally, the suture was made using a black 00 silk thread (Fig. 9).

Post-operative care is prescribed, including applications of ice packs, an antibiotic (amoxicillin 500 mg 4 times a day), an analgesic (ibuprofen 400mg 3 times a day) and mouthwash starting the next day.

The patient is seen again 24 hours later for washing with hexetidine, ten days later for removal of the sutures, one month later for a check-up, then one year later with a panoramic radiograph which shows bone filling and reappearance of the roof of the canal. broken tooth (Fig. 10).

The immediate clinical examination and that at one month revealed no sign of labio-mental paresthesia.

Discussion:

What are the causes of such a complex inclusion? Before analyzing the different causes and explanations of our case, it seems necessary to mention the histology and the embryology of mandibular molars.

Histology-Embryology:

The third molar arises from the same oral epithelial layer as the first and second molars and the wisdom tooth forms from the primitive dental lamina [12,13]. This lamina, formed from mesenchymal cells around the sixteenth week in utero, will continue its cell multiplication at the distal end to successively form the germs of the first, second and then third permanent molars. It is only around the ninth month that the germ of the second molar appears but that of the third appears around 4 or 5 years [4,12,13]. The germ of the third molar therefore derives from the dental lamina of the second, itself derived from that of the first (Fig. 11).

Thus, the wisdom tooth, whose adamantine bud is located behind the second molar, is presented as a replacement tooth for the latter. These buds have a gubernaculum dentis which attaches them not to the gum, like the other teeth, but to the gubernaculum of the first molar. This may explain the most frequent orientation of lower wisdom teeth, oblique in mesial version. Its evolution follows a posterior concavity curve: This is the Capdepon recovery curve [4].

The eruption of the mandibular molars will simply and schematically follow two movements:

first one the germ moving by its own development and following of course the mandibular bone growth, the second one begins with the formation of the root which bears the already formed crown. The tooth gradually straightens its axis and moves towards the

retromolar space, the size of which depends on the posterior growth of the mandible [4,7].

So, by referring to the histology and embryology we can suppose in the observed case that the germ of the second molar underwent during its evolution a movement in mesial version, while continuing its evolution, taking the germ to a horizontal position. However, the germ of the third molar derives from the same dental lamina of the second molar continue his evolution.

The twisting movement of the germ of the second molar carried with it the germ of the third molar which also evolved in a horizontal position; this may explain the position of the two mandibular molars. The origin of the movement can be traumatic or other.

This assumption remains hypothetical and requires further embryological studies to be confirmed.

Our therapeutic attitude is justified by the irrecoverable position of the second molar, and by the frequency of infectious accidents. The CT scan allowed us to better understand the relationship between the tooth and the mandibular canal. It allowed us to carry out a complete and precise pre-operative assessment which guided our surgical procedure. This was an indication for this kind of radiological examination [14].

Conclusion:

Lack of space or posterior crowding syndrome is the most common cause of impacted mandibular molars. The diagnosis should be made as soon as possible. It is based on the clinical examination and especially on the radiological assessment; an early diagnosis makes it possible to avoid this kind of inclusion and if not to reduce the complexity of the cases.

Pictures:

Figure 1: Clinical view of the right molar region.

Figure 2: Panoramic X-ray: agenesis of the 2nd mandibular premolars and the presence of the deciduous molar on the right side.

Figure 3: Horizontal section individualizing the radiolucent image encompassing the second molar and the distal apex of the 1st molar.

Figure 4: Axial section showing the collapse of the roof of the dental canal on the right side and the bone framework that separates the two impacted molars. On the left side, the apices of the molar are distant from the lower dental canal.

Figure 5: A panoramic reconstruction of the CT scan showing the position of the impacted molar with the lower dental canal in profile.

Figure 6: Clinical view of the right side after wisdom tooth extraction. Note the appearance of the crown of the molar only which proves the accuracy of the scan.

Figure 7: After release of the bone framework that separates the two molars, appearance of the impacted 2nd molar.

Figure 8: After extraction of impacted molar. Note the appearance of the inferior dental nerve.

Figure 9: Separate stitch sutures in black 00 silk thread.

Figure 10: Panoramic X-ray one year postoperative.4

Figure 11: Position of the dental germs at the cap stage (from Cantaloube D and Fusari J.P 1991). 1: oral epithelium, 2: dental lamina, 3: follicular sac, 4: dental papilla, 5: enamel organ.

Running Title: Second mandibular Impacted molar.

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